

CHEMISTRY OF RARE EARTHS. PART XI. UROTROPIN AND ANTIPYRENE COMPLEX OF TETRATHIONATES OF RARE EARTHS

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Preparation and properties of complexes of La, Ce and Pr tetrathionates with urotropin and antipyrène have been described

Dutt and his co-workers described the preparation and properties of several urotropin and antipyrène complexes of rare earth thiosulphates (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 533) and dithionates (this *issue*, p. 272). Rare earth dithionates have long been known as highly soluble hygroscopic salts with several molecules of water of crystallisation. Gadolinium salts as described by Sarkar (*Ann. chim.*, 1927, x, 8, 239) was so hygroscopic that it could not be analysed. Tetrathionates have not been described. We also failed to prepare the tetrathionates of rare earths, sample being highly soluble and refusing to crystallise. As the solubilities of the dithionates are much diminished by combination with urotropin and antipyrène, their isolation is easier. Similar behaviour with rare earth tetrathionates was expected, and isolations of the tetrathionates of rare earths in combination with urotropin and antipyrène have been made with success.

EXPERIMENTAL

Purified rare earth salts, which had been used in Part X (*loc. cit.*) of this series, were employed in the following preparations.

Lanthanum-urotropin Tetrathionate.—To a concentrated solution of lanthanum nitrate (5 g.) in cold water was added an aqueous solution of urotropin (10 g.) and the solution was filtered from any precipitate. To this solution was then added a saturated solution of sodium tetrathionate dropwise, when beautiful white crystals separated. These were left for sometime, and filtered under suction. The crystals were washed with ice-cold water and recrystallised from least quantity of cold water.

The compound is colorless and crystalline. It is moderately soluble in water. The salt is quite stable in the solid state and in aqueous solution in the cold. An aqueous solution of the salt decomposes on heating with separation of sulphur and lanthanum hydroxide. It melts above 250° with decomposition. [Found: La, 18.31, 18.42; S, 25.73, 25.48; N, 14.71, 14.61. $\text{La}_2(\text{S}_4\text{O}_{12})_3 \cdot 4\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires La, 18.41; S, 25.43; N, 14.83 per cent].

Cerous^{III}-urotropin tetrathionate was prepared in the same way as the lanthanum salt using cerous nitrate. In properties it resembles the previous salt in all respects. [Found: Ce, 18.32, 18.65; S, 25.56, 25.48; N, 14.72, 14.54. $\text{Ce}_2(\text{S}_4\text{O}_{12})_3 \cdot 4\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires Ce, 18.52; S, 25.40; N, 14.81 per cent].

Praseodymium-urotropin tetrathionate, was prepared in the same way as the above mentioned compound using praseodymium nitrate. The salt separated in beautiful

green crystals. In other respects it resembles the other salts. [Found: Pr, 18.52, 18.68; S, 25.56, 25.37; N, 14.92, 14.82. $\text{Pr}_2(\text{S}_4\text{O}_6)_3 \cdot 4\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires Pr, 18.61; S, 25.34; N, 14.79 per cent].

Lanthanum-hexa-antipyrene Tetrathionate.—To a concentrated solution of lanthanum nitrate (3 g.) was added cold aqueous solution of antipyrene (5 g.). Crystals separated, if any, were dissolved in the least quantity of cold water and filtered. To this filtered solution was then added dropwise a cold saturated solution of sodium tetrathionate when beautiful colorless crystals separated. It was filtered under suction, washed with ice water and dried first between folds of filter paper and finally in air.

The compound is colorless and crystalline. It is moderately soluble in water and quite stable in the solid state for several days. [Found: La, 13.62, 13.45; S, 18.58, 18.65; N, 8.22, 8.18. $\text{La}_2(\text{S}_4\text{O}_6)_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires La, 13.38; S, 18.48; N, 8.08 per cent].

Praseodymium hexa-antipyrene tetrathionate was prepared in an identical manner as the previous compound. Its properties are very similar to the latter. [Found: Pr, 13.72, 13.39; S, 18.46, 18.58; N, 8.21, 8.12. $\text{Pr}_2(\text{S}_4\text{O}_6)_3 \cdot 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires Pr, 13.45; S, 18.44; N, 8.07 per cent].

Method of Analysis.—Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate after oxidation with alkali and bromine and after separation of rare earth from this solution with ammonia. Rare earths and nitrogen, in urotropin complexes, were estimated as shown in Part X (*loc. cit.*). Nitrogen in antipyrene compounds was estimated by Duma's method of combustion.